

Influence of Shear on the Templated Crystallization of Poly(butylene terephthalate)/Single Wall Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposites

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Abstract

The templating effect due to shear and single wall carbon nanotubes, SWCNT, on polymer crystallization has been studied in a series of nanocomposites based on poly(butylene terephthalate) (PBT). By using a rheometer, a step shear was applied to the molten polymer and, after shear cessation, the sample was immediately cooled down to the crystallization temperature. Crystalline development, in real time, was investigated by small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) with the synchrotron radiation beam parallel to the free film surface. SWCNT bundles template polymer lamellae to grow perpendicular to the SWCNT surfaces in a shish kebab fashion even under quiescent conditions. Due to the power of SWCNT as nucleating agents the shear rate has a minor effect on the crystallization kinetics. However, the fraction of oriented material increases significantly with shear rate. The results indicate that SWCNT act as nuclei stabilizers providing surfaces which favor polymer crystallization.

1.Introduction

Since the discovery of carbon nanotubes by Iijima in the early nineties¹ the scientific activities in this field have followed an exponential increase due to the remarkable physical properties of this novel form of carbon¹⁻⁵. Single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) are shown to be promising reinforcing elements, with Young's moduli in the TeraPascal (TPa) range, for a new generation of nanocomposite materials⁴⁻⁶. A typical SWCNT sample consists on micron-size aggregates, frequently referred to as bundles or ropes, in which single nanotubes self-assemble into a two-dimensional hexagonal close packed lattice⁷. Upon mixing with a polymeric matrix a homogenization of the nanotubes down to the nanometer level is attempted by different procedures including compounding, sonication and shear among others⁴⁻⁶. In general, typical polymeric nanocomposite processing involves solidification, either by crystallization or by vitrification, from a molten state distorted by a combination of shear and elongational flow fields. The effect of processing induced flow fields on the nanostructure of polymers and nanocomposites is crucial because of the profound impact on their physical properties^{4,5, 8-11}. The effect of shear fields, mimicking those used in industrial processing on the structure of SWCNT polymer nanocomposites remains almost untreated until now. Recent experiments have shown that, additionally to the nucleating effect of SWCNT¹², this type of carbon nanotubes are very efficient in templating oriented polymer crystal growth¹³⁻¹⁷. Different processing routes were used including injection molding^{14,17}, fiber spinning¹⁵ and crystallization from solution¹³. In these works it was shown that the SWCNT surface imposes to polymer crystals a growth direction perpendicular to the nanotube longitudinal main axis. It is known that both injection molding and fiber spinning involve a complex thermal and flow history to the sample making difficult to separate the effect on polymer crystallization of flow fields from thermal gradients. However, by using either a rheometer or a shear cell thermal and flow effects can be separated by choosing the appropriate combination of shear strain, shear rate and temperature⁸⁻¹¹. Until now, as far as X-ray scattering is concerned, most of the shear induced crystallization studies have been carried out by means of rotating parallel plates equipment in which the X-ray beam impinges the sample perpendicular to the free surface of the rotating plates⁸⁻¹¹. This disposition is quite appropriate because guarantees a nearly constant shear rate on the explored sample volume.

However, upon dealing with SWCNT/polymer nanocomposites, due to the high aspect ratio of SWCNT, the nanotubes may tend to adopt orientations in which their main axis is located preferentially parallel to the surface plates. Then, in this case a X-ray beam impingement with the beam parallel to the surface of the rotating plates can be advantageous because orientation effects parallel to the rotating plates can also be probed. The aim of this work is to study the crystallization of nanocomposites based on SWCNT under the controlled shear fields provided by a rheometer¹⁸ in which the X-ray beam reaches the sample parallel to its free surface (Fig.1). Our main objective is to answer two basic questions:1) Under which conditions SWCNT template an oriented crystallization? and 2) How can shear rate be used to control templating?. To accomplish both tasks a matrix of Poly(butylene terephthalate)(PBT) was selected due to the extensive body of previous shear-induced crystallization on this polymer¹⁰. In addition PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites can be prepared by “in situ” polymerization rendering rather good SWCNT dispersions¹⁹.

2.Experimental

2.1 Polymer samples

For this study several nanocomposite samples of poly(butylene terephthalate)(PBT) ($M_w \approx 15000$ g/mol) with different amounts of oxidized single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) (from CNI Technology Co., Texas, USA, synthesized by using the HiPco[®] method) were prepared. The Raman spectra show that the investigated SWCNT consist of different diameter populations²⁰ ranging from about 0.6 nm to 1.4 nm. The PBT/SWCNT nanocomposite preparation scheme follows an “in situ” polymerization strategy which has been described in detail elsewhere¹⁹. The nanocomposite was extruded from the reactor by compressed nitrogen and subsequently it was pelletized and injection molded with a Baby Plast, Model 6/10 (Cronoplast S.L. Comp) machine into long pieces with a rectangular cross section of 2×4 mm². The injection molding parameters were: injection pressure 25 bar, melt temperature 240-250 °C, mould temperature 40 °C, hold time 6 s and cool time 20 s. Nanocomposite films of about 0.1 mm thickness were obtained by compression molding at 240°C for 2 minutes and subsequently quenched under constant pressure at a cooling rate of $\sim 300^\circ\text{Cmin}^{-1}$.

2.2 Rheo-SAXS measurements

Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements were performed at the ID2 beam line at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, France. The synchrotron radiation was monochromatised to provide a wavelength of $\lambda=0.1$ nm. SAXS patterns were recorded by a two dimensional CCD camera (FReLoN Kodak CCD, with an input area of 100mm x 100mm). The sample to detector distance was fixed to 2640 mm. Typical beam size at the sample position is 0.1×0.1 mm². An initial data reduction is accomplished in order to correct for detector distortion and to normalize to the intensity of the primary beam. Shear was applied to the sample by using a RS300 (HAAKE) rheometer. The main characteristic of the adapted rheometer has been published elsewhere¹⁸. The rheometer has been modified to accommodate a truncated cone of $r = 3$ mm in diameter at the end of the inner cylinder as schematically depicted in Fig. 1. The gap, set to $h = 0.6$ mm, was filled with about six films piled up and parallel to the incident X-ray beam. Under these conditions the maximum shear rate applied to the sample is given by $\dot{\gamma}_m = (r/h)\Omega$, where Ω is the angular speed. Fig. 2 describes schematically the type of shear experiments we accomplished. A step shear is applied to the molten polymer for a certain time at a temperature higher than its melting temperature, $T_m = 225.3$ °C. After cessation of the shear the sample is immediately cooled down to the crystallization temperature, T_c , at a cooling rate of 10 °C/min. Subsequently, crystallization was followed by SAXS as a function of time. By this procedure the flow and the crystallization processes can be effectively separated²¹. Different maximum shear rates, $\dot{\gamma}_m$, of 0, 5, 10 and 20 s⁻¹ were applied for different times in order to obtain a maximum constant strain of 2000 %. Two-dimensional SAXS images were taken immediately after the polymer reached the crystallization temperature $T_c = 208$ °C. The data acquisition time for each 2-D scattering pattern was typically 0.1 s. An air scattering pattern was also collected. The air scattering pattern was used for background correction of the scattering data. Subsequent analysis of the X-ray data was carried out using the corrected and normalized scattering patterns.

2.3 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was used to visualize the microstructure and morphology of PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites. We used a Nanoscope IIIA Multimode from Veeco operating in the tapping mode. The samples for AFM were prepared by spin coating on a silicon wafer (100) (Wafer World Inc.) from a trifluoroacetic acid solution (20 g l^{-1}). A precise volume of 0.1 ml of the polymer solution was instantly dropped by a syringe on a rectangular (about $2 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$) silicon substrate centered on a rotating plate at 2380 rpm for 30 s. Samples were stored at room temperature preventing them from dust.

2.3 Data analysis

2.3.1. Oriented fraction

The 2-D SAXS patterns were treated in order to obtain different magnitudes including the integrated intensity, the oriented fraction and the Hermans orientation factor. The scattering pattern was first azimuthally integrated in order to obtain the scattering intensity as a function of the scattering vector $s = 2\lambda^{-1}\sin\theta$, where 2θ is the scattering angle. The orientation fraction was obtained on the basis of a custom experimental strategy described elsewhere¹⁰ which is schematically shown in fig.3. Basically, the 2-D SAXS pattern is divided into two quadrants chosen to represent the scattering along the meridian, chosen parallel to the shear direction, and the equator respectively. The integrated intensity within a cake depicted in Fig.3 is calculated in the two quadrant defining the magnitudes I_{mer} and I_{eq} for the meridian and equator contribution respectively. Subsequently an orientation fraction parameter Φ is defined by:

$$\Phi = \frac{I_{mer} - I_{eq}}{I_{mer} + I_{eq}} \quad (1)$$

2.3.2. Orientation function

Hermans orientation function is commonly used to estimate the orientation of a sample from the analysis of Wide Angle X-ray Scattering data. In addition, it has been demonstrated that it is also useful to evaluate the orientation of crystalline lamellae from a SAXS pattern²². In this case the Hermans orientation function f_2 is given by:

$$f_2 = \frac{3\langle \cos^2 \phi \rangle - 1}{2} \quad (2)$$

with:

$$\langle \cos^2 \phi \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\pi/2} I_i \sin \phi \cos^2 \phi}{\sum_{i=0}^{\pi/2} I_i \sin \phi} \quad (3)$$

being I_i the scattered intensity at the i -th polar angle ϕ . In our case, this calculation was done by azimuthal cake integrations with three cake sizes in order to have an estimation of the error in the values of f_2 . The zero position for ϕ was set $\phi = 0$ at the meridian of the pattern and ϕ runs counter clockwise. Meanwhile the initial and final angles for the integration were chosen to be 90° and 180° , in order to avoid the shadow of the beamstop. The f_2 function was normalized by shifting the background to zero. In this case, the orientation function $f_2=1$ when the scattered intensity concentrates on the meridian and $f_2 = -0.5$ when the scattered intensity concentrates on the equator. For an isotropic pattern a value of $f_2=0$ is expected.

3.Results

3.1. Shear Induced Crystallization of the PBT matrix.

Fig. 4a shows a series of 2-D SAXS patterns for PBT taken at $T_c=208^\circ\text{C}$ after the application of a step shear (shear rate of 10 s^{-1}) at $T = 240^\circ\text{C} > T_m$. Starting from an amorphous undercooled melt at $t=0\text{ s}$ crystallization takes place with time as revealed by the appearance of an essentially isotropic ring associated to the characteristic long-spacing of the lamellar stacks¹⁰. Fig. 4b shows the total integrated SAXS intensity as a function of time for different shear rates. Fig. 4c represents the oriented fraction, calculated as described above, as a function of time for the different shear rates investigated. Only for the higher shear rate, 10 s^{-1} , a significant initial orientation is observed. The negative value of Φ in this case indicates a preferential orientation of the scatterers on the meridional direction. The amount of oriented fraction tends to diminish as a function of time. A similar behaviour has been previously reported for PBT under shear conditions¹⁰. Thus, in the early

stages of the crystallization process a certain orientation can be estimated. This effect has been attributed to the formation of row nuclei parallel to the flow direction. Due to chain relaxation, row nuclei break down into point like nuclei leading to a very small oriented fraction. Fig. 5a represents the half time of crystallization as a function of shear rate at $T_c=208$ °C. As expected for PBT, crystallization kinetics tends to become faster as shear rate increases¹⁰. A slight increase of the half time is observed for a shear rate of 20 s^{-1} . This effect can be due to a possible chain scission mechanism under the present experimental conditions. In qualitative agreement with previous results¹⁰, long spacing values tend to decrease with increasing shear rate (see fig.5b for PBT). For comparative purposes Fig.5a-b also shows the results obtained for the nanocomposites samples.

3.2. Crystallization of PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites under quiescent conditions.

Fig.6a shows the integrated SAXS intensity as a function of crystallization time for PBT and a PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite under quiescent conditions at $T_c=208$ °C. As previously reported, even a modest amount of carbon nanotubes produce a strong enhancement of the crystallization kinetics of the polymer matrix. Carbon nanotubes provide nucleation surfaces over which polymer chain can easily grow^{5,15}. However, more striking is the fact that, as shown in fig. 6b, a significant orientation appears for the nanocomposite even under quiescent conditions. This is revealed by the strongly anisotropic SAXS pattern obtained at the end of the crystallization experiment as shown in Fig.7. Here the initial and final SAXS patterns have been included in the two first columns of fig.7. While PBT exhibits almost no oriented fraction at the end of the crystallization process, the nanocomposite shows a significant amount of oriented fraction. It is noteworthy that, as revealed in fig.7, for the nanocomposite the orientation changes from one with the scatterers parallel to the shear direction (Fig.7 , t_0), to other one in which the scatterers are perpendicular to the shear direction (Fig.7 , t_f). At this point it is important to mention that this orientation effect is emphasized by the parallel film disposition of the experimental set-up (Fig.1). As a matter of fact the SAXS pattern of the PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite obtained on perpendicular disposition shows no signs of orientation (last column of fig. 7). These facts can be taken into account for the interpretation of oth the orientation fraction and the Hermans orientation function

represented in fig.6b and 6c respectively. Here it is detected that PBT starts, at the beginning of the crystallization process, with a small but negative value of Φ and f_2 indicating oriented scatterers in the direction of the shear. During crystallization, orientation in PBT tends to approach a zero level as previously reported¹⁰ and discussed in the previous paragraph. On the contrary, the PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite starts with a negative value of Φ and f_2 indicating oriented scatterers in the direction of the shear (SAXS pattern for t_0 in Fig.7) but, as crystallization proceeds, orientation switches towards positive values indicating oriented scatterers perpendicular to the shear direction (SAXS pattern for t_f in Fig.7) .

3.3. Crystallization of PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites after step-shear.

Fig.8 exhibits a series of SAXS patterns taken at specific crystallization times for PBT and the PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites at $T_c = 208$ °C after the application of a step-shear (shear rate of 5 s^{-1}). The long spacing associated to the maximum in scattering intensity are smaller than those observed under quiescent conditions. L values do not vary significantly with nanotube concentration but tend to decrease with increasing shear rate (fig.5b). While PBT does not exhibit significant orientation features during crystallization, the sample with SWCNT shows a strong concentration of the SAXS scattering intensity on the meridian. This is the case for all the nanocomposites investigated. Fig.9a, shows the integrated intensity for a series of PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites during crystallization at $T=208^\circ\text{C}$, under a shear rate of 5 s^{-1} . Similarly to the quiescent crystallization case, the presence of SWCNT provokes a significant increase of the crystallization kinetics. Fig.9b and 9c show the oriented fraction and Hermans orientation functions, respectively, as a function of crystallization time. It is clear that the final oriented fraction increases with the amount of SWCNT from ≈ 0.1 to above 0.25. The development and evolution of the oriented fraction during the crystallization process appears to be complex and requires a deep examination of the Hermans orientation functions (fig. 9c). The initial orientation factor for PBT takes negative values and tends to approach zero as crystallization proceeds. The sample with 0.01 wt % of SWCNT starts with negative values of the orientation factor but soon ($t>50 \text{ s}$) evolves towards positive values. For the samples with higher SWCNT concentration positive orientation factors are always found along the crystallization

process. In these cases no significant variation of the orientation factor is observed during crystallization. These effects can be visualized by focusing on the initial and final SAXS patterns for the different nanocomposites shown in fig. 8. Samples with 0 and 0.01 weight % of SWCNT exhibit at the initial time SAXS patterns with an excess of scattered intensity in the equatorial region indicating an orientation in the direction of the shear. However at the final crystallization times the scattered intensity of the SAXS patterns concentrates in the meridian part indicating a predominant orientation perpendicular to the shear direction. Fig.10a and 10b show the oriented fraction and the Hermans orientation function respectively at the end of the crystallization process as a function of the shear rate for the different samples. On the one hand, the orientation fraction achieved at the end of the crystallization process increases with shear rate for the nanocomposites. On the other hand, the presence of SWCNT seems to be the dominant factor in the final orientation rather than shearing conditions.

4. Discussion

The shear induced crystallization of PBT has been previously described as being dominated by point nuclei¹⁰. As compared with polyolefins, polycondensation polymers like PBT, do not reach the critical molecular weight above which, for a certain shear rate, molecular segments remain oriented long enough to template anisotropic crystallization^{8,24}. Therefore for crystallization at high temperatures, the initial rodlike nuclei which appear as a consequence of shear tend to relax breaking into point nuclei leading negligible orientation at the end of the crystallization process¹⁰. In our case this effect manifest itself by the initial existence of a certain negative orientation factor which tend to vanish as crystallization proceed rendering a final isotropic crystallization material (fig.4). The low and negative values of the Hermans orientation factor (fig. 6) indicate an initial orientation of the polymer chain constituting the nuclei parallel to the shear. Our results are in qualitative agreement with previous measurements done in PBT¹⁰. Here Li et al have proposed a model like the one represented in fig.11A in which initial row nuclei formed after shear application evolve, due to relaxation, to point nuclei rendering to an isotropic crystallization situation. This poor scenario for oriented crystallization of PBT changes dramatically by the addition of modest quantities of SWCNT. Even under quiescent

crystallization, SWCNT template rather effectively oriented crystallization as revealed by the data presented in fig.6 and the SAXS patterns shown in fig. 7. From the initial anisotropic SAXS pattern for the PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite (fig.7) a negative value of the Hermans orientation factor can be estimated (fig.6). This fact can be attributed to the scattering of SWCNT which lay preferentially with their main axis parallel to the free surface of the film. As crystallization proceeds the Hermans factor evolves towards positive values because the scattered intensity tends to concentrate in the meridian. The oriented SAXS pattern for the same sample (fig.7) observed at the end of the quiescent crystallization indicates that a certain amount of crystalline lamellae have grown perpendicular to the free film surface. Accordingly, SWCNT act as heterogeneous nuclei providing surfaces over which PBT crystals can grow orientated. In the initial stages of crystallization, SWCNT provide surfaces where PBT crystals can grow perpendicular to the SWCNT surface and therefore perpendicular to the film surface. SWCNT bundles act as shish units in such a way that the nanocomposite structure resembles that of a shish kebab. As crystallization proceeds those polymer crystals not in contact with the SWCNT surfaces exhibit little preference to remain oriented. Although shear affects significantly both the half time of crystallization and the long spacing of PBT (fig.5), it has a minor effect on these two magnitudes for the nanocomposites. This can be understood as due to the efficient nucleation power of SWCNT. However, the final fraction of oriented crystalline material in the PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites increases significantly with the shear rate (Fig.10). and, in some cases, it reaches a maximum and later decays. Thus, we propose that the presence of SWCNT modifies the crystallization process as schematically described in fig.11B. After shear, the polymer melt develops row nuclei in the initial stages. When SWCNT are present, nuclei far away from the SWCNT surface can relax but those close to these surfaces do not. Consequently, SWCNT provide surfaces which stabilize nuclei enhancing oriented crystallization with crystalline lamellae growing perpendicular to the SWCNT surface and therefore perpendicular to the free surface of the film. This effect is expected to operate in addition to the usual quiescent nucleation effect of SWCNT. As crystallization proceeds polymer material located far away from SWCNT surfaces grow without any preferred orientation and this provokes the decay of the oriented fraction in the final stages of crystallization. Shish kebab structures induced by SWCNT have been

reported for nanocomposites based on polyethylene^{13,15,24} and its oligomers²⁵. A similar morphology has been reported in polyethylene/sorbitol composites²⁶. For PBT/SWCNT, on the basis of SAXS experiments, the existence of shish kebab microstructure was proposed in injection molded samples^{14,17}. Fig. 12 shows two AFM images with different magnification of a PBT/0.2 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite. Here, the presence of a characteristic SWCNT bundle is clearly seen in Fig. 12 for the lower resolution. A magnification of one of the bundle branches, fig. 12 bottom panel, indicates the formation of crystalline blocks in a shish kebab fashion along the main axis of the SWCNT bundle.

4. Conclusions

The influence of the shear on templating of single wall carbon nanotubes on polymer crystallization has been studied in PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites. SWCNT bundles template crystallizing polymer lamellae perpendicularly to the SWCNT surfaces in a shish kebab fashion even under quiescent conditions. Due to the power of SWCNT as nucleating agents shear has a minor effect on crystallization kinetics. However, under shear conditions, the fraction of oriented material increases significantly with shear rate. We propose that the effect of SWCNT is to counterbalance nuclei destruction providing surfaces which stabilize nuclei and enhance the oriented crystallization of lamellae which grow perpendicular to the SWCNT surface. Our experiments performed under shear emphasize the variety of crystalline structures which may appear in SWCNT nanocomposites when processed under the combination of complex force fields and temperature gradients.

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Legends to the figures

Fig.1. Scheme of the experimental set-up for Rheo-SAXS experiments. The sample (made of stacked films) fills the gap, of height h , between a truncated cone, of radius r , and the substrate plate. The cone rotates with an angular speed Ω . The films room temperature are parallel to the incident X-ray beam.

Fig.2. Schematic description of the step shear experiments. After reaching a temperature higher than the melting temperature, T_m , the sample is subjected to a step-shear for a certain time. After shear cessation the sample is cooled down to the crystallization temperature, T_c .

Fig.3. Example of the data analysis strategy used to extract the oriented fraction, Φ , from the two dimensional SAXS patterns to measure the integrated intensities, I_{mer} and I_{eq} , corresponding to the meridian and the equator scattered contributions respectively. The pattern corresponds to a SWCNT/0.2 wt % SWCNT sample crystallized at $T_c=208$ °C after a step shear (shear rate of 5 s^{-1}).

Fig.4. (a) SAXS patterns for PBT at different times, taken at $T_c=208$ °C after the application of a step shear (shear rate of 10 s^{-1}) at $T=240$ °C above the melting temperature. **(b)** Total integrated SAXS intensity during crystallization of PBT as a function of time for different shear rates applied. **(c)** Oriented fraction as a function of crystallization time for PBT under different shear rates.

Fig.5. (a) Half time of crystallization for PBT as a function of shear rate. **(b)** Long spacing as a function of shear rate for different SWCNT wt %. $T_c=208$ °C.

Fig.6. Time variation of: **(a)** the integrated SAXS intensity, **(b)** the orientation fraction and **(c)** the Hermans orientation function for PBT and a PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite under quiescent conditions at $T_c=208$ °C.

Fig.7. Initial, t_0 , and final, t_f , SAXS patterns for PBT and a PBT/0.1 wt % SWCNT under quiescent crystallization at $T_c = 208^\circ\text{C}$ with the sample parallel (first two columns) and perpendicular to the x-ray beam (last column).

Fig.8. Series of two dimensional SAXS patterns taken at specific crystallization times at a shear rate of 5 s^{-1} for PBT and the PBT/SWCNT nanocomposites at $T_c = 208^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig.9. Variation of (a) SAXS integrated intensity, (b) oriented fraction and (c) Hermans orientation factor for a series of SWCNT/PBT nanocomposites during crystallization at $T_c=208^\circ\text{C}$, in a SMT experiment with a shear rate of 5 s^{-1} .

Fig.10. (a) Oriented fraction and (b) Hermans orientation function at the end of the crystallization process for the different samples and shear rates investigated.

Fig.11. Schematic view of the morphological development during shear crystallization. **(A) for PBT** (according to ref. 10): (a) Random coil before shear. (b) Shear-induced row nuclei, (c) Formation of primary point nuclei due to relaxation of row nuclei, (d) Isotropic crystal growth. **(B) for PBT/SWCNT:** (a) Random coil before shear, (b) Shear-induced row nuclei, (c) Type I nuclei, far away from SWCNT-surfaces, relax into primary point nuclei. Type II nuclei stabilize onto the SWCNT-surfaces and originate anisotropic crystal growth on the SWCNT surface (d) Subsequent isotropic crystal growth originated by point nuclei.

Fig.12 . AFM images of a PBT/0.2 wt % SWCNT nanocomposite. Upper and bottom panel are different magnifications indicated by the scale bar. Left and right pictures correspond to the height and phase images respectively.

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig. 4

Fig.5

Fig.6

Fig.7

Fig.9

Fig.10

Fig.11

Fig.12